

Chemical Aspects of Biological Oxidations.*

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In my last address to the Society, I pointed out that the most fundamental processes taking place on the surface of the earth depend on the following reversible reaction,

One side of the above reaction was discussed last year and in this address I shall consider some aspects of the chemistry of respiration.

Introduction.

The scientific study of life phenomenon was initiated by Lavoisier when he declared in 1780 that *life is a chemical process* ("La vie est une fonction chimique"). This savant clearly recognised from his experiments that life processes are those of oxidation resulting in the liberation of heat. With a clarity of vision, which is the unique characteristic of this investigator, he established that the quantity of oxygen absorbed and of carbon dioxide excreted depends principally on (1) food, (2) work, and (3) temperature, within a few years of his discovery that oxygen supported combustion. Writing in 1849, Regnault and Reiset stated that modern researches have amply confirmed these far-reaching conclusions of the illustrious savant. ("Les recherches modernes ont confirme ces vues profondes de l'illustre savant."). Oxidation is the central life process sustaining the complicated machinery of the living.

The substances undergoing oxidation in the animal body comprising of carbohydrates, fats and proteins are not oxidised readily under ordinary conditions outside the body, although in the animal and plant tissues they are burnt up with ease into their end products.

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The problem of the mechanism by which animals and plants can accomplish the oxidation of the food materials so readily has occupied the attention of scientists since the days of Lavoisier. It is generally believed that oxygen must in some way be activated in the living tissues.

Induced Oxidation of Carbohydrates, Fats, Proteins, etc., and the Induced Oxidation Theory of Biological Oxidations.

Some interesting observations made in the author's laboratory seem to point to far-reaching conclusions with regard to the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats and proteins in normal healthy animals and plants.

In several publications from this laboratory, it has been shown that substances like glucose, starch, cane sugar, glycogen, butter, egg-white, egg-yellow, tartrates, citrates and fatty acids like palmitic and stearic acids, and numerous other substances, which are not directly oxidised by atmospheric oxygen at ordinary temperatures, can be oxidised by simply passing air through their solutions or suspensions, when they are mixed with compounds like sodium sulphite or freshly precipitated ferrous, cerous, manganous and other hydroxides, all of which undergo oxidation readily. It is important to note that in each case, the substance is oxidised to carbon dioxide and water, without the formation of any intermediate compound. A molecule of acetic acid containing two carbon atoms, and a molecule of stearic acid which contains eighteen carbon atoms, are equally well oxidised to carbon dioxide and water; the same is the case with alcohol containing two carbon atoms and glucose containing six carbon atoms.

One cannot but be struck by the close analogy between these slow and induced oxidations and biological oxidations in a normal individual or a plant. The normal metabolism of carbohydrates and fats gives rise to carbon dioxide and water only and to no intermediate products. Such products as glycuronic acid from glucose and diacetic acid from fatty acids, make their appearance only in their abnormal metabolism, as in intoxication with phenol, chloral, etc., or in diabetes or in fasting or as a result of continued vomiting or in poisoning with drugs like phlorhizin, etc. It is also interesting to note that exactly similar intermediate products are obtained in the case of rapid oxidation with hydrogen peroxide and a ferrous or ferric

salt (Dakin, Kostychev, Jolles, Dhar and Chakravarti). But the products of slow and induced oxidation of carbohydrates and fats are exactly identical with those of the normal metabolism of these substances in the animal body or plant tissue.

The behaviour of some of the polybasic acids is also instructive. Oxalic acid, the simplest member of the group is very rapidly oxidised by many laboratory reagents, but is oxidised with great difficulty in the animal body. Malonic, succinic, glutaric, tartaric and citric acids, however, are readily oxidised in the body, although they are more stable than oxalic acid towards many oxidising agents. It will be of interest to note that oxalic acid and oxalates are oxidised with very great difficulty by induction *in vitro* whilst tartaric acid and tartrates and citric acid and citrates can be readily oxidised by induction.

A systematic investigation of induced oxidations of the above type has been carried out in the author's laboratory. Suffice it to say here that oxidation of a wide variety of compounds has been effected by atmospheric oxygen in the presence of inductors like insulin, glutathione, sodium sulphite, colloidal phosphorous, freshly precipitated ferrous, cerous, manganous, uranous and other hydroxides at ordinary temperature (20-30°). Our recent experiments show that in presence of traces of copper compounds the induced oxidation of glucose, tartrate, etc., is markedly facilitated. Hence it appears that in the treatment of metabolism diseases or anæmia, the addition of traces of copper salts to iron or manganese preparations may be useful. It is highly significant that many of these substances yield carbon dioxide and water, products of normal metabolism. Knowing what one does of the products, which are formed by the action of other oxidising agents, one cannot but be impressed by the parallelism, which this suggests. Not only the products of induced oxidation are carbon dioxide and water but the oxidation of these substances to carbon dioxide and water is quantitative. It seems probable, therefore, from the analogy of these experiments *in vitro*, that biological oxidations can be classed under induced reactions; and that there exists in the animal body and plant tissues readily oxidisable substances, the oxidation of which induces the oxidation of food materials. Moreover, most of the vitamins, which are absolutely necessary for healthy life have been found to be good reducing agents capable of taking up oxygen directly from air and thus help the induced oxidation of food materials with which they are associated.

*Comparative Experiments on the Oxidation of Proteins,
Carbohydrates and Fats.*

Inductor—cerous hydroxide. 60 Litres of air passed in 9 hours.

Substance.					Amount of substance oxidised.
Egg-white	...	...	...	...	83.3%
Egg yellow	...	...	...	...	69.4
Starch	...	...	...	...	57.2
Glucose	...	...	...	...	36.5
Butter	...	...	...	...	29.9

These substances fall in the following order according to their ease of oxidation. Egg-white > egg-yellow > starch > glucose > butter. In other words, proteins are more readily burnt than carbohydrates, which in their turn, are oxidised with greater ease than fat. The order is the same as that given by Voit, who stated that "the metabolism in the body is not proportional to the combustibility of the substances outside the body; but protein which burns with difficulty outside, metabolises with the greatest ease than carbohydrates, while fat which readily burns outside is the most difficultly combustible in the body." This conclusion was arrived at by Voit from actual feeding experiments. These results show with what great success, biological oxidations have been imitated outside the body. The foregoing results can throw light on the problem of protein metabolism in the animal body. It is well known that the increase in metabolism is greater in the case of protein than with any other food-stuff. This increased metabolism called the *specific dynamic* action of protein by Rubner, has not been satisfactorily explained by physiologists. According to our results the protein is more readily oxidised than carbohydrates and fats and it is expected that in the animal body protein is more readily burnt than carbohydrates and fats and that is why more heat is generated in an unit time than with carbohydrates and fats. The recent experiments of Atma Ram and Dhar show that under comparable conditions the amino acids like α -alanine and aspartic acid are oxidised to a greater extent than cane sugar, glucose, sodium palmitate, stearate, oleate, etc., when exposed to air and light *in vitro*.

Recent Evidence in favour of the Induced Oxidation Theory.

Within recent years some evidence has accumulated in favour of this theory of biological oxidations, because most of the biologically active compounds like insulin, ascorbic acid (vitamin C), carotene (pro-vitamin A), lactoflavin (vitamin B₂), "ovoflavin," the oxidation ferments of Warburg, etc., have been found to be excellent reducing agents, capable of taking up oxygen directly from air. The energy obtained from these oxidations seems to initiate the oxidation of the food materials. Some important work on yellow oxidation enzymes has been published by Warburg and Christian (1932-33). The yellow enzyme is believed to contain a colloidal carrier and a pigment which on irradiation in alkaline solution produces the substance C₁₃H₁₂O₂N₄ (m.p. 320°). The *leuco*-form of the enzyme in presence of atmospheric oxygen produces the yellow enzyme and H₂O₂. With methylene blue the yellow enzyme and *leuco*-methylene blue are produced. Since the enzyme contains no metal, its oxygen transport is not inhibited by CO or HCN. It is believed by Warburg that this yellow enzyme causes the oxygen transport in anaerobic lactic acid cultures and is present in all cells including those of higher animals. On the other hand, Keilin (1933) has concluded from spectroscopic investigation of some bacteria that the shading in the yellow (5900Å) and the band in the red (6300Å) are not the absorption bands of the oxygen transporting enzyme as believed by Warburg but are those of derivatives of cytochrome and probably of its component—a.

Moreover, recent research has shown that vitamin C seems to be identical with ascorbic acid, which is a marked reducing agent capable of inducing the oxidation of food materials. It is believed that vitamin C, whilst retaining most of its activity may be reversibly oxidised and the labile structure of ascorbic acid fits it well for such function. According to Müller (1933) and others the reducing property of aqueous humour of cattle and rabbit is also due to vitamin C. Ascorbic acid can be oxidised reversibly and irreversibly and it is to the double function of oxidation and reduction in the reversible change that the acid probably owes its biological activity. The parallelism between the reducing power and the antiscorbutic potency of plant extracts has been investigated by several workers. Tillmans, Hirsch and Jackisch (1932) have reported that the vitamin C content and the reducing capacity are, under many conditions, strictly parallel. Moreover, the reducing substance studied by them may be oxidised, like hexuronic acid, in a reversible and irreversible manner.

Similarly Peters and collaborators (1929-33) have shown that the brains of polyneuritic pigeons have a high lactic acid content and the brain tissue from such pigeons has a sub-normal oxygen intake and that on adding a concentrate of vitamin B₁ to the tissue, the oxygen intake is enhanced.

Recently a number of naturally occurring colouring matters, which are water soluble nitrogenous dyes, have been obtained from different sources. These dyes called flavins or lyochromes have been isolated from animal liver and kidney and from egg-white and milk whey. These dyes are believed to be related to the oxidation ferments prepared by Warburg and Christian (1932). The dye obtained from egg-white is termed "ovo flavin" and is reduced and decolourised by reducing agents and regains its colour when shaken in air. The change flavin $\rightleftharpoons$ leucoflavin is believed to depend on the transference of oxygen. The crystalline orange-brown dye from whey named "lactoflavin" has the composition C₁₇H₂₀O₆N₄ and resembles "ovo flavin" closely in composition and absorption spectrum. Both of these flavins are not only related to vitamin B₂, but lactoflavin is believed by Kuhn and his colleagues (1933) to be identical with vitamin B₂. During the last few years important researches on natural polyene pigments (lyochromes) have been published by P. Karrer and R. Kuhn and their collaborators. These pigments are widely distributed in the vegetable and animal kingdoms and comprise hydrocarbons, alcohols, xanthophylls, phyto xanthins, ketones, carboxylic acids and carboxylic esters. Carotene contains three distinct substances, two of which α - and β -carotenes, contain 11 double bonds and like vitamin A promote growth of animals. β Carotene is more allied to vitamin A biologically and chemically and Kuhn and collaborators have advanced the view that one mole of β -carotene can form two moles of vitamin A in the animal body as represented in the following equation,

It is believed that kryptoxanthin, is also a pro-vitamin A like α -, β - and γ -carotenes.

*Glutathione and Internal Secretion as Inductors of
Biological Oxidations.*

It is interesting to note that experiments carried on in the author's laboratory have shown that insulin and glutathione can act as inductors

in the oxidation of glucose solutions at ordinary temperature by simply passing air. Hopkins (1921), Harrison (194), Dixon (1929), Meldrum (1930) and others were successful in oxidising amino acids, proteins and fats by air in presence of glutathione. They were, however, unable to oxidise carbohydrates in the same manner. We have observed that in presence of small amounts of cerous, ferrous, manganese or cupric hydroxide either occurring singly or in mixtures of two or three, the addition of glutathione markedly increases the oxidation of glucose.

In this connection, it will be of interest to note that Oparin (1921) has stated that a dipeptide, chlorogenic acid $C_{32}H_{38}O_{11}$ occurs in over a hundred different plants and it is readily oxidised in air losing four hydrogen atoms and forming a green product. It is believed that chlorogenic acid is more particularly active in the oxidation of amino acids, peptides and peptones forming ammonia, carbon dioxide and aldehyde. The author is of opinion that the oxidation of chlorogenic acid by air induces the oxidation of food materials, especially of proteins.

Moreover, glutathione is of common occurrence in animal and plant tissues. The colour by which glutathione is recognised is less intense in vegetable than in animal tissues. The oxidation of glutathione by air is likely to induce the oxidation of food materials in the vegetable and animal tissues as it does *in vitro*. As the amount of glutathione appears to be less in vegetable tissues than in the animal ones, the intensity of oxidation in the animal cells is greater than in plant cells. This is perhaps one of the factors which lead to a less active metabolism in plants than in animals.

Holmes (1926) has found that in general the tumour cells contain abnormally small amounts of reduced glutathione and may be slow in reducing the dipeptide added in the oxidised form. Rat sarcoma and carcinoma tissues were found to be deficient in the respiratory pigment cytochrome. Crabtree (1929) has shown that the glycolytic activity of tumours exerts a checking effect on their respiration. Very recently Heinlein (1932) has reported that the glutathione content of tumours (Ehrlich mouse carcinoma, Rous sarcoma and human carcinoma) is lower than that of normal organs. If this contention of Holmes and Heinlein that cancerous tissues contain abnormally small quantities of reduced glutathione and the respiratory pigment cytochrome is correct, it appears that the oxidations of glucose and lactic acid are less in such tissues because the inductors glutathione and

cytochrome exist in smaller amounts in cancerous than in normal tissues. These observations of Holmes and Heinlein lend support to the author's view that biological oxidations are really cases of induced oxidations.

It will be interesting to note that the glutathione content of muscles in which oxidation processes are supposed to take place at an intense rate is small as will be evident from the following values.

Tissues.	Fed animal (dog).	Tissues.	Fed animal (dog).
Liver	0.21	Spleen	0.09
Lungs	0.08	Heart	0.08
Muscle	0.05	Testicle	0.06
Kidney	0.14	Brain	0.06
		Adrenaline	0.00

It is well known that roughly two-thirds of the body energy necessary for animal life are obtained from the slow combustion of glucose and as the glutathione content in muscles is small, it can be concluded that glutathione is not the chief catalyst or inductor in carbohydrate oxidation in the body.

F. G. Benedict (1932) has come to the conclusion that the relatively low heat production with cold blooded animals in comparison with the warm blooded animals of the same size is due to the difference in the distribution of the blood carrying the three important factors of metabolism, *viz.*, oxygen, nutrients and hormones and that increased blood flow is associated with increased metabolism. In the cold blooded animals, the amount of blood is relatively less than in warm blooded animals. The heat production in the body seems to be controlled by the blood supplied to the tissues. Where there is a liberal blood supply to the tissues, the heat generation can be high, where the blood supply is low, the heat production must be low also. The blood distribution is not determined by the metabolism, because with man the same blood distribution may permit his metabolism to be increased 1000 % in extreme cases. Lusk (1919) has stated that in starvation, amongst the various body organs, the greatest loss in weight is suffered by the glands and that their activity is greatly reduced.

Hence it seems likely that the internal secretions possibly acting as inductors, largely control animal oxidation. In starvation, the

amount of internal secretion available for accelerating the oxidation decreases and hence the metabolism is decreased. In violent exercise, the metabolism is highly increased probably due to the increase in the oxygen intake and a greater supply of internal secretions from the various glands. It appears that although glutathione and other reducing agents present in the blood are of some importance in animal metabolism, the chief inductor seems to be the internal secretions.

Respiratory Pigments and Plant Respiration.

Palladin (1908) has reported that when plant tissues are extracted with boiling water, a colourless chromogen is obtained and these chromogens called by Palladin as "respiratory chromogens" are believed to be widely distributed in the plant kingdom. It will be of interest to note that Palladin assumes with others that the atmospheric oxygen oxidises only the hydrogen of the respiratory chromogens and this reaction is aided by the peroxidases and is not concerned with the oxidation of the carbon of the food materials.

Haas and Hill (1925, 1926) have extracted a colourless chromogen from the leaves of *Mercurialis perennis*. This chromogen named hermidon by Haas and Hill has a marked affinity for oxygen. It has been suggested by Haas and Hill that hermidon takes part in the respiration of *Mercurialis perennis* and when the respiration of the plant is high in summer and spring, the amount of hermidon in the leaves is abundant.

A blue pigment has been observed by Roach (1925) in slightly sprouted potatoes placed over-night in a vacuum dessicator in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide and then powdered. When air is allowed to enter, the blue colour becomes more marked and finally, a light yellow colour is obtained. It appears that potatoes contain a compound like hermidon.

The isolation of chlorogenic acid by Oparin and its probable usefulness in plant respiration has already been pointed out.

Different authors have advanced different views on plant respiration but there is not much agreement in these views. The hypothesis of Palladin has already been discussed. Professor Blackman of Cambridge (1928) from his experiments with Parija on the respiration of ripening apples has postulated that there are at least four stages in the process of respiration, *viz.*,

- (i) The hydrolysis of the carbohydrate to hexoses.
- (ii) The hexoses pass to an activated form.

(iii) The activated hexose undergoes glycolysis with the formation of lactic and pyruvic acids, acetaldehyde, etc.

(iv) In presence of oxygen, these products of glycolysis undergo oxidation to carbon dioxide and water. In absence of oxygen, i.e., in anaerobic conditions, alcohol and carbon dioxide seem to be produced. According to Blackman, the velocity of glycolysis is the slowest of the various stages and thus controls the velocity of the respiration.

On the other hand, Kostychev is of opinion that alcoholic fermentation and sugar respiration are connected phenomena and he represents the two phenomena as follows:—

According to Kostychev, there are two steps in the process of normal respiration in plants viz., (i) the anaerobic cleavage, and (ii) their subsequent oxidation. In other words, Kostychev is of opinion that the first stage of oxygen respiration is anaerobic respiration and anaerobic and oxygen respirations are connected. In this connection, it will be of interest to note, that parasitic worms (*ascaris*), earth worm (*lumbricus*) *infusoria*, leech, etc., produced carbon dioxide and sometimes fatty acids as well when deprived of oxygen and hence anaerobic life of lower organisms is also possible. On the other hand, experiments in the absence of oxygen cannot proceed far with warm blooded animals without causing death, because the tissues and especially, the nervous tissues appear to be extremely sensitive to absence of oxygen.

The views of Blackmann and Kostychev rest on the assumption that glucose is the only material available for plant respiration. But it is a well established fact that proteins and fats are also used up in plant respiration. Hence, it appears that so far no comprehensive theory of plant respiration, embracing the metabolism of the three chief varieties of food materials, carbohydrates, fats and proteins, has been advanced. It seems to the author that the mechanism involved in the oxidation of food materials in the plant is the same as in the animal metabolism, and the phenomenon of induced oxidation of food materials in the

presence of easily oxidisable substances like glutathione, chlorogenic acid, Palladin's "respiratory chromogens", Keilin's cytochrome, insulin, etc. form the basis of plant and animal respiration. It is well known that the conversion of glucose into alcohol and CO_2 and the oxidation of glucose to CO_2 and water are exothermal chemical changes. The formation of alcohol from glucose according to the equation,

is a typical case of an auto-oxidation and reduction process well known in chemistry such as the following decompositions:

the well known Cannizzaro reactions are also exactly similar. These auto-oxidation and reduction processes are less exothermic than the reactions involved in the complete oxidation of the reducing substances. Thus for the same amount of glucose the heat generated is greater when it is oxidised to CO_2 and water than in its conversion into alcohol and CO_2 . That there is a greater possibility of the occurrence of an auto-oxidation and reduction reaction than a reaction involving complete oxidation is due to the fact that the energy difference in the original reacting substances and the products formed is greater in the reactions involving complete oxidation than in the auto-oxidation reduction processes.

The plant physiologists like Kostychev, Blackmann, Palladin and others being familiar with anærobic respiration have based their views regarding the mechanism of plant respiration on the similarity of the processes involved in ærobic and anærobic respirations. In the fermentation of glucose forming alcohol and CO_2 several enzymes are believed to take part and some of these enzymes have also been detected in plants, *e.g.* hexosephosphatase in peameal, ketonaldehyde mutase, carboxylase, etc. Moreover, several co-enzymes which activate the enzymes have also been found in some plants. The enzymes aided by the co-enzymes can behave as typical catalysts in accelerating the exothermal reaction,

In other words, as far as anaerobic respiration is concerned the theories of Palladin, Kostychev and Blackman have a large amount of experimental evidence in their support. On the other hand, the schemes of these plant physiologists seem unsatisfactory when we consider aerobic respiration, which is certainly of greater importance in normal plant life than anaerobic respiration. It is well known that ordinary oxidising enzymes are unable to oxidise even small amounts of glucose in presence of air. What is the mechanism by which the labile intermediate products formed from hexose by the action of zymase in the scheme of Kostychev are oxidised to CO_2 and water in presence of air? In Blackman's scheme, in the process of glycolysis caused by the group of enzymes present in zymase, a number of intermediate compounds, e.g. methylglyoxal, lactic acid, pyruvic acid and acetaldehyde are supposed to be formed. Moreover, in the Embden-Meyerhof scheme (1933) recently advanced, the intermediate formation of pyruvic acid, acetaldehyde, etc., has been assumed. Now most of these compounds which are supposed to be formed as intermediate products in fermentation and in respiration are incapable of taking up oxygen directly from the air and undergo oxidation to CO_2 and water, which are the final products of respiration in the animals and plants under normal conditions.

On the other hand, not only these substances but all food materials are finally oxidised to CO_2 and water in the animal and plant tissues in presence of air. Consequently the theories of Palladin, Kostychev and Blackman do not explain the final process in aerobic respiration.

Agencies helping Biological Oxidations.

It seems to the author that the following agencies are effective in bringing about the oxidation of food materials not only in animal life but also in plant respiration.

(1) Reducing agents like glutathione, chlorogenic acid, ascorbic acid, Palladin's "respiratory chromogens," Keilin's cytochrome, ovoflavin, lactoflavin, internal secretions, etc. These substances take up oxygen directly from the air and induce the oxidation of food materials.

(2) The surface of the plant and animal cells.

(3) The presence of small quantities of iron and possibly traces of manganese and copper compounds.

(4) Mild alkalis and phosphates.

(5) Sunlight.

All these agencies seem to have their relative importance in causing the oxidation of the food materials possible in the plant and animal tissues, although they are not oxidised in the air outside. There is reason to believe that in animal oxidation the internal secretions play an important rôle. It is well known that Nature hardly depends on one agency in carrying on its mechanism and in bringing about the oxidation of glucose and other oxidisable materials, seems to take recourse to the foregoing agencies, which have been shown to accelerate the oxidation of food materials by air.

The induced oxidation theory of the mechanism of biological oxidations has more experimental evidence in its support than the surface oxidation theory of Warburg and the dehydrogenation theory of Wieland. Meyerhof failed to oxidise glucose by air on a charcoal surface and the theory of Wieland is not helpful in understanding the mechanism of the oxidation of glucose. (*cf.* Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry", 1932, pp. 18-20).

Are the "Acetone Bodies" Products of Normal Metabolism?

Many physiologists believe that β -hydroxybutyric acid, acetoacetic acid and acetone are intermediate products of normal metabolism, that the diabetic cannot further oxidise them, and that as such they are excreted in the urine.

It is established beyond doubt that the excretion of acetone bodies in the urine occurs only in conditions in which carbohydrates are either not being utilised owing to metabolic deficiency or is missing from the food. To the former category belong diseases like diabetes or cases of poisoning with drugs like phlorhizin; to the latter, cases of continued vomiting or voluntary abstention from carbohydrate food. When acetonuria has made itself manifest as a result of lack of carbohydrates in the food, the administration of such food materials, causes the prompt disappearance of acetonuria or ketosis. It appears that for the complete combustion of fats, carbohydrates must be metabolised at the same time.

Various explanations have been suggested for the anti-ketogenic effect of carbohydrates. Geelmuyden (1904) has assumed a combination of acetone bodies and carbohydrates to occur before the oxidation of the former can take place. Woodyatt (1916) suggests that a coupled

reaction takes place between acetoacetic acid and glucose, glyceric aldehyde or some simple sugar, the sugar being oxidised and the acetoacetic acid being simultaneously reduced. Ringer (1914) assumes a combination of glucose and β -hydroxybutyric acid in order that the latter may be oxidised and Shaffer (1922) has arrived at the conclusion that two molecules of acetoacetic acid enter into reaction with one of glucose. There seems to be little experimental evidence in favour of these views on the anti-ketogenic properties of carbohydrates.

The author (1925) has advanced the following explanation based on experimental observations on the velocity of oxidation of carbohydrates, fats and proteins occurring singly or in mixtures: Under normal conditions, the heat and energy of the body are derived from the simultaneous combustion of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. When as a result of special conditions, carbohydrate is not oxidising more fat and protein must be burnt in order to maintain the body temperature and energy at its normal level. Hence in an unit time more fat would be burning than under normal conditions and combustion is likely to be incomplete, so that acetone bodies would be formed. It has been observed that whenever there is rapid combustion of fat, as for instance, in hyperthyroidism, there is the elimination of acetone bodies. The same is the case *in vitro* as well. Chakravarti and Dhar (1929) have observed that in the rapid oxidation of fatty acids by hydrogen peroxide and ferric salts, there is the formation of acetone bodies. They have also observed that if the rate of oxidation of fats be slowed down, as is the case when carbohydrates (*e.g.* glucose) are present, the amount of acetone bodies produced diminishes. Palit and Dhar (1930) have further observed that in the slow and induced oxidation of fats, acetone bodies are not formed at all, but only carbon dioxide and water, the products of normal metabolism.

It is evident, therefore, that acetone bodies are not products of normal metabolism, but result from abnormal conditions. The author has suggested that under normal conditions, fats are mainly burnt in the animal body directly to carbon dioxide and water, without the formation of intermediate products. An objection may be raised as to how a fatty acid molecule containing 18 carbon atoms can be directly oxidised to carbon dioxide and water without the formation of intermediate products. Many physiologists are of opinion that acetoacetic acid, with four carbon atoms in the molecule, undergoes complete oxidation to carbon dioxide and water without the formation of intermediate products. If a molecule with four carbon atoms can be directly

oxidised then the direct oxidation of more complex acids appears to be not impossible.

The hypothesis of the author that when fats are rapidly oxidised in the absence of carbohydrates and proteins intermediate toxic substances are produced, is supported by the observation of Pirschle (1926) that acetaldehyde is formed in the respiration of many fat-containing germinating seeds such as *Helianthus*, *Linum*, *Cannabis*, *Brassica*, *Raphanus* and *Cucurbita*. It is well known that the respiration of germinating seeds is very intense and hence when the fats in the germinating seeds are oxidised rapidly intermediate products such as aldehydes, etc., are formed and the oxidation of fats does not proceed to completion with the formation of carbon dioxide and water. It appears that the metabolism of fat in plants is allied to its metabolism in animals.

*Oxidation effected by Hydrogen Peroxide differs from
Biological Oxidations.*

The supposed similarity between the oxidations taking place in the living body and those brought about by hydrogen peroxide *in vitro* (Dakin, Kostychev, and Jolles) is believed to lend strength to the peroxide theory of biological oxidations. Thus Dakin writes (1912) "An extraordinarily close similarity as regards the types of reactions exists between the two sets of phenomena. Thus normal saturated fatty acids in the body undergo oxidation in the β -position, butyric acid yielding acetoacetic acid, acetone and other products; hydrogen peroxide alone of all the various chemical oxidising agents brings about precisely the same reaction. Amino acids and ketonic acids, such as leucine and phenylpyruvic acids are oxidised to lower fatty acids with the liberation of carbon dioxide and either ammonia and water. Glucose may be oxidised in the body to glycuronic acid, while hydrogen peroxide is the only reagent capable of effecting this change outside the body. A great many other biochemical reactions of less strikingly characteristic type such as the oxidation of simple alcohols, aldehydes, etc., may be reproduced *in vitro* by means of hydrogen peroxide."

If we consider this statement, it will be at once clear that the similarity between the oxidations in the animal body and those *in vitro* effected by hydrogen peroxide is only superficial. The intermediate products selected here for bringing the similarity into relief, namely glycuronic acid in the case of glucose, acetoacetic acid, acetone and other products in the case of butyric and other fatty acids, and carbon

dioxide and ammonia in the case of amino acids are not products of normal metabolism but are only obtained in certain pathological conditions. The end products of normal metabolism of glucose and fatty acids in a healthy individual are carbon dioxide and water. The introduction of camphor, chloral, etc., into a normal as well as diabetic person leads to the excretion of combined glycuronic acids.

Dakin (1908) has shown that ammonium butyrate on being oxidised with hydrogen peroxide and a ferrous salt forms acetone, acetoacetic acid, acetaldehyde, etc. Chakravarti and Dhar have shown that volatile aldehydic or ketonic products are formed when carbohydrates, fats and nitrogenous substances are oxidised with hydrogen peroxide and a ferric salt at 37°. Hence *in vitro* when the food materials are rapidly oxidised, acetaldehyde and other intermediate products are obtained but when the oxidation of food materials is slow as in the cases of induced oxidation obtained by passing air, complete oxidation of food stuffs takes place. In animals and plants, similar behaviour is also expected. The author has emphasised that in normal health the food materials taken in the body are completely oxidised into carbon dioxide and water without the formation of intermediate products, just as food materials are oxidised completely to carbon dioxide and water, when air is passed through their solutions or suspensions in presence of inductors or in sunlight. Intermediate compounds are only formed in the diseased condition of the animal body and plant tissues or when the nutrient material is oxidised quickly in the plants or animals.

It has been observed that volatile aldehydic or ketonic products along with carbonic acid are formed when carbohydrates, fats and nitrogenous substances are oxidised by hydrogen peroxide and an iron salt at 37°, whilst only carbon dioxide and water are obtained and there is complete oxidation when the above substances are oxidised by air in presence of ferrous hydroxide as inductor. It appears, therefore, that the intermediate iron peroxide obtained in the case of hydrogen peroxide and an iron compound must be different from that formed with the ferrous compound and oxygen, because the products of oxidation are different in the two cases.

Oxidation of Mixtures of Carbohydrates, Fats and Proteins

Palit and Dhar (1928-1930) have carried on experiments on the induced oxidation of mixtures of carbohydrates, fats and proteins with

each other and have arrived at the important conclusion that the presence of any one of these substances, which is itself undergoing oxidation, retards the oxidation of the other.

Now in the normal health, the heat and energy of the body are supplied to the system from the simultaneous combustion of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. Our experimental results conclusively prove that the oxidation of fat is retarded by carbohydrates and perhaps less powerfully by proteins. It seems fairly certain now that the presence of either one or both of the above substances, which are undergoing oxidation, retards the oxidation of the third. It is, therefore, evident that in the presence of a large excess of carbohydrates and fats, little protein should burn. The protein-sparing qualities of carbohydrates and fats were discovered from feeding experiments by some of the earliest students of metabolism, and it is believed that carbohydrate is the more efficient of the two in sparing proteins. It has also been proved that the withdrawal of carbohydrates from the food increases the protein metabolism. Moreover, in diabetes, when the sugar passes out unoxidised, there is considerable waste of protein. The experimental results of Palit and Dhar provide for the first time a scientific explanation of these empirical observations of physiologists.

On the basis of the above results, a satisfactory explanation can be given on the onset of glycosuria, following the intake of phosphorus, arsenic, phlorhizin or other poisons. All these substances are marked reducing agents and therefore, in accordance with the general principle laid down in the opening paragraph of this section, they produce retardation of the oxidation of the glucose in the animal body. Hence some of the glucose escapes unoxidised in the urine and more protein should be metabolised in order to keep up the normal supply of the body heat and energy. In this connection it is interesting to note that phosphorus injections raise the protein metabolism of fasting dogs to 250, 260, 283, 248, 183 and 164 per cent of the normal. The percentage increase of protein metabolism in phlorhizin glycosuria is 540, 450 and 340. Moreover, it has been reported that administration of whisky favours the production of glucose in a diabetic. Apparently the easily oxidisable carbohydrates, which act as negative catalysts in the oxidation of fats, are necessary for the complete combustion of the latter.

If the acetone bodies are to be ascribed to the rapid but incomplete combustion of fats which is shown to take place in the diabetic,

it follows that, not only in diabetes but also in all other conditions, where there is rapid combustion of fats and little oxidation of carbohydrates, there should be acidosis and acetonuria. Indeed these conclusions are confirmed by experiments on human beings and animals carried out by several physiologists. Thus Bar (1905) has reported that a simple withdrawal of carbohydrates is followed in normal human beings accustomed to a mixed diet, and also in apes, by an acidosis, that is excretion of oxybutyric acid, acetoacetic acid and acetone with coincident increased elimination of ammonia. Deprivation of carbohydrate increases the body's need of fat and this flooding of the metabolic mill with fats results in their incomplete oxidation with the consequent production of acetone bodies. In starvation, or as a result of continued vomiting, acetonuria is observed after some days from the beginning of starvation, when most of the body store of glycogen has been utilised. In all such cases where acetonuria sets in as a result of simple carbohydrate deficiency in the food, the administration of carbohydrates causes the disappearance of ketosis. In hyperthyroidism too, where there is a rapid oxidation of fat, glycosuria and some times actual manifestations of diabetes have been observed.

If the oxidation of fats can somehow be retarded, then in diabetes there should be a marked decrease in the elimination of acetone bodies. Thus xylose, gluconic acid, citric acid, propionic acid, glutamic acid, glutaric acid, etc., have been found to decrease the formation of acetone bodies in diabetes. All the substances are utilised by the diabetic. Hence smaller amounts of fat need to be burnt. The author is of opinion that all these reducing substances, which are themselves oxidised in the body act as negative catalysts in the oxidation of fats, thus favouring the slow but complete oxidation of the latter with the resulting decrease of the acetone bodies.

Proteins also exert antiketogenic properties, although to an extent smaller than carbohydrates. Very little carbohydrate and a great deal of fat are taken by the Eskimos; but they eat an abnormally large amount of protein. In their case, the large amounts of proteins act like carbohydrates in retarding the oxidation of fats and thus assist their complete oxidation.

Use of Alkali Tartrates and Citrates in Diabetes and Fasting.

Our experimental results obtained in these laboratories, show that by the addition of sodium tartrate, the amount of potassium oleate

oxidised by induction in 30 hours by 73 litres of air is considerably decreased. In the case of ferrous hydroxide as inductor, in presence of sodium tartrate the percentage of potassium oleate oxidised is 7.9, whilst under identical conditions and in absence of sodium tartrate the percentage is 40.7. The corresponding results with cerous hydroxide as inductor are 16.8% and 45.1% respectively. Hence it is clear that the addition of a tartrate markedly decreases the velocity of the oxidation of potassium oleate. Moreover, the presence of oleate retards the velocity of the oxidation of sodium tartrate.

These results seem important from the point of view of the treatment of diabetes and prolonged fasting. Under normal conditions the heat and energy of the body are derived from the simultaneous combustion of carbohydrates, fats and proteins. When as a result of special conditions such as diabetes, carbohydrate is not burning more fat and protein must be burnt in order to maintain the body temperature and activity at its normal level. Hence in unit time, more fat would be burning than under normal conditions, and the combustion of fat would be incomplete, so that acetone bodies would be formed. Chakravarti and Dhar (1929) have observed that in the rapid oxidation of fatty acids by hydrogen peroxide and ferric salts there is a formation of acetone bodies. They have also observed that if the rate of oxidation of fats be slowed down, as in the case when carbohydrates (*e.g.*, glucose), are present, the amount of acetone bodies formed diminishes. Palit and Dhar (1930) further find, that in the slow and induced oxidation of fat, acetone bodies are not formed at all, but only carbon dioxide and water, the products of normal metabolism.

Our experimental results show that just as carbohydrates decrease the velocity of oxidation of fats, similarly tartrates and citrates can also decrease the velocity of the oxidation of fats. Hence a tartrate or a citrate, apart from its power of acting as a buffer in removing the excess of hydrogen ion (H^+) generated in the body, may serve as an antiketogenic substance like a carbohydrate. Thus the tartrates or citrates in drinks are likely to prove beneficial in the treatment of diabetes and long continued fasts, because in such cases the body has not lost the power of oxidation and is likely to utilise the tartrates and citrates as food along with the fats of the body.

In the plant kingdom, there are also examples of formation of intermediate substances in the process of respiration. Succulent plants

do not evolve carbon dioxide when placed in the dark, although oxygen absorption is active. In these cases organic acids like malic, oxalic etc., are formed and when the concentration of these acids becomes large, evolution of carbon dioxide as in normal plants takes place. It is assumed that this peculiar behaviour is associated with the massive structure of the succulent plants and fleshy fruits and the difficulty of the movement of the gases. It appears that in these plants, the supply of oxygen necessary for the complete oxidation of food materials to carbon dioxide and water is inadequate due to the slow movement of the gases. In some bacteria, acids are also formed in their oxidative activities.

The experiments of Stephenson and Whetham (1923) on the Timothy grass bacillus are of interest from the view point of the oxidation of a mixture of fats, proteins and carbohydrates in metabolism. The bacillus was cultivated at 37° on a medium containing ammonium phosphate as a source of nitrogen and glucose as the source of carbon. The p_H of the medium was 8.0. The sugar was used up in about three weeks but fats and proteins accumulated during this period. After three weeks, the amount of fats was burnt but the protein was not yet oxidised. There was no intermediate product of oxidation but carbon dioxide was given off. When the sugar was being oxidised, the respiratory quotient was high but later on in the process of fat combustion, the respiratory quotient became less. These results are easily explained from the view point that the complete oxidation of fat requires the presence of a negative catalyst which in this case is the protein, just as in the case of the food consumed by the Eskimos already referred to in which the large fat consumption is facilitated by the presence of considerable amounts of proteins. Another important point has been brought out by the investigations of Stephenson and Whetham. They studied the metabolism in slightly alkaline medium (p_H 8) and it has already been mentioned that Dhar and collaborators have observed that the oxidation of food materials is assisted by the presence of mild alkalis. It appears that the oxidation of fats and glucose in the experiments of Stephenson and Whetham was also facilitated by the alkaline medium.

Carbon-nitrogen Ratio in Natural Systems undergoing Oxidation.

It is well known that in soil, which is well-aerated, the chemical changes affecting the carbon and nitrogen present in the soil are

intimately connected. The combined nitrogen existing in the soil can form nitrate only if the ratio of C to N is smaller than 10. When the proportion of carbon is greater, the excess is oxidised to CO_2 and the nitrogen remains as complex protein. When, on the other hand, the proportion of nitrogen becomes greater than the above ratio, the nitrogenous compound is changed into ammonia and nitrate, which may be absorbed by the plant or lost from the soil by different agencies. The observations of Leighty and Shorey (1930), however, show that in the majority of soils examined by them the carbon-nitrogen ratio varied from 7 to 15 and in extreme case the ratio could be as small as 3 and as large as 35. It seems to the author that the soils examined by Leighty and Shorey were not properly aerated for a sufficiently long time. The constant ratio is reached in soils which are sufficiently aerated. The value of the constant may vary with the climatic conditions because the relative velocity of the oxidation of carbonaceous compounds may not be the same at all temperatures.

The constancy of the carbon-nitrogen ratio in the soil has been ascribed to the activities of micro-organisms but it will be evident from the following considerations that the constancy of C to N is maintained even in the absence of bacteria in many natural systems undergoing oxidation in air and in the soil.

Dhar (1921) has observed that in the presence of sodium arsenite, which becomes oxidised when added to sodium sulphite exposed to air, the velocity of the oxidation of sodium sulphite by air is markedly retarded. Similarly, the presence of carbohydrates, which are themselves oxidised when mixed with a sulphite, ferrous hydroxide or cerous hydroxide, markedly diminishes the velocity of the oxidation of the last named substances. We have arrived at the generalisation that in oxidation reactions the phenomenon of negative catalysis is observed when the catalyst is a reducing agent. The experimental results obtained in these laboratories conclusively prove that the oxidation of fat is retarded by carbohydrates, and perhaps less powerfully by proteins. It is therefore, evident that in the presence of a large excess of carbohydrates or fats, little protein is burnt.

It will be interesting to note that in starvation the ratio of carbon to nitrogen metabolism (oxidation) is also not far from 10 as will be evident from the following results.

Animal	...	Dog.	Fowl.	Guinea pig.	Rabbit.
Ratio of C and N oxidised in starvation	...	9.5	10.8	7.6	9.7

If the starvation is continued further the value becomes less than 10 as will be seen in the following results obtained with a dog kept on starvation.

Days of starvation ...	4th-13th.	14th-15th.	16th-23rd.	24th-30th.	31st-35th.	36th.	37th.	38th.
Ratio of C and N oxidised in starvation ...	10.3	9.3	9.01	8.6	8.0	6.0	5.8	5.5

Following the lead of Doryland (1916) it has been assumed that the energy requirements of the bacteria present in the soil control the relative oxidation of the different groups of organic substances present therein. It is well known that the percentage of the energy utilised by the bacteria from an oxidation reaction is exceedingly small and thus it seems hardly probable that such inefficient processes should be able to regulate the various oxidation reactions taking place in the soil. The retarding influence of different carbohydrates and carbonaceous substances in the processes of ammonification and nitrification, is observed with different bacteria, fungi, etc., of different energy and food requirements, and is not regulated by their demands, but forms a part of a universal phenomenon taking place in the animal, plant and in soil and *in vitro* in which it is always observed that a readily oxidisable organic substance can act as a negative catalyst in the oxidation of another substance.

Are Organic Acids formed in Plant Respiration?

Mayer (1887) stated that in the plant respiration under certain conditions, oxalic and malic acids are formed and that sugars are produced from these acids in presence of light. The amount of malic acid in succulent plants increases at night and decreases in presence of light. It is of interest to note that Sir J. C. Bose (1924) has reported that *Hydrilla* can undergo marked photosynthesis in sunlight in the complete absence of carbonic acid but when fed with dilute solutions of malic or oxalic acid. In presence of sunlight, the organic acids can partially decompose into carbonic acid and are also oxidised to carbon dioxide and water, which undergo photosynthesis.

There is considerable difference of opinion regarding the origin of these organic acids detected in plant respiration. Some authors believe that sugars form organic acids whilst others ascribe them to proteins.

Sir J. C. Bose (1924) has observed that the *Hydrilla* plants become strongly acidic in summer (April), but the acidity disappears when the rainy season (July) sets in. It seems likely that in summer in the tropics, the temperature of the water in the ponds becomes high and the amount of dissolved oxygen which is necessary for plant respiration, becomes less. Hence the available oxygen essential for respiration decreases and the oxidation of the food materials present in the *Hydrilla* has to proceed in an insufficient supply of oxygen resulting in the production of organic acids, which are intermediate products of metabolism and not in the final products—carbon dioxide and water. There is another factor which may facilitate the formation of acids in the *Hydrilla* at the high temperature of the tropical summer. It has already been mentioned that the velocity of respiration is greater, the higher the temperature. Hence in summer months, the oxidation of food materials in the *Hydrilla* is rapid but it has already been emphasised that there is greater likelihood of the formation of intermediate products of metabolism and not of the final products—carbon-dioxide and water, when the metabolism of food materials is rapid than when it is slow. Hence at high temperatures, the *Hydrilla* forms acids by respiration. It is well known that the respiration of germinating seeds is very intense and that is why, we can expect the formation of intermediate products in the respiration of germinating seeds. Thus Pirschle (1926) reported the formation of acetaldehyde in the respiration of many carbohydrate, protein and fat-containing germinating seeds.

It appears, therefore, that organic acids, aldehydes and other intermediate products are formed in plants (specially in fleshy fruits and succulent plants) under special circumstances when the oxidation of food materials takes place very rapidly or in a limited supply of oxygen. In the animal body also, intermediate products are formed under similar conditions.

*Photo-oxidation of Carbohydrates, Fats and Nitrogenous Substances
by Air in Sunlight and Influence of Light on Respiration.*

It has been shown by Dhar and Sanyal (1925) that methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol and glycerol are oxidised by passing air at the ordinary temperature in the presence of sunlight.

Pa'it and Dhar (1928-1934) have made a systematic investigation of the oxidation of various substances by air in sunlight at the

ordinary temperature. They have shown that different carbohydrates, glycogen, urea, glycine, hippuric acid, α -alanine, sodium urate, potassium palmitate, stearate, oleate, sodium formate, tartrate, oxalate, lecithin, cholesterol, butter, milk, egg-white, egg-yolk, etc., can be oxidised photochemically by passing air.

Moreover, it has been shown that in the presence of zinc oxide, and ferric and uranium nitrates, which act as photo-sensitisers, the amount of oxidation of the foregoing substances is greatly accelerated.

All the above substances are completely oxidised to carbon dioxide and water without the formation of intermediate products. Hence light accelerates the oxidation reactions on which animal life depends. Palit and Dhar have also carried out comparative experiments on the oxidation of egg-white, egg-yolk, starch, butter, glucose, cane sugar, and glycogen in sunlight, and the following are the results, amount oxidised being given in parantheses: egg-yolk (60.9%) egg-white (31.25%), starch (38.2%), butter (31.8%), glucose (13.6%), cane-sugar (7.8%), glycogen (7.5%).

It appears, therefore, that egg-yolk is the most easily oxidisable substance in presence of light; then come starch and also butter, which are oxidised with greater ease than sugars, which are the least oxidised. These results on the oxidation of food materials by air in sunlight are suggestive, and the beneficial influence of light in the treatment of disease may be due to an increased metabolism in light.

The following results obtained by Glitscher and Hasselbach (1926) show that light can actually penetrate through epidermis. The rays of shorter wave-length are absorbed by the thinnest layers of the epidermis. On the other hand, rays of longer wave-length can penetrate to appreciable depths.

Wave-length	Percentage transmission by epidermis	
	0.1 mm. thickness.	1 mm. thickness.
4360 $\text{\AA}$	59	0.5
4050	55	0.3
3660	49	0.09
3540	42	0.02
3130	30	0
3015	8	0
2990	2	0
2970	0.01	0

From their researches on the photo-oxidation of food materials by air in sunlight at the ordinary temperature, Palit and Dhar have concluded that the light absorbed by the system accelerates the metabolism of food materials in the body. The person thus has a sense of well-being when exposed to light and disease is avoided. Sunlight is appreciably transmitted by the epidermis, and by absorption of light the body cells are activated, and hence increased oxidation of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins takes place. It seems to be accepted on all hands that several diseases are caused by defective metabolism, and therefore sunlight should prove efficacious in the treatment of these diseases.

The results on the photo-oxidation show that under identical conditions butter is oxidised to greater extent than glucose in presence of sunlight. It is generally believed that rickets is associated with defective fat metabolism and it is expected from our experimental observations that rickets would be more amenable to light treatment than diabetes as the oxidation of fat is more facilitated by light than that of glucose. Several medical men have reported that the metabolism of children or adult exposed to light may be 40% higher than in the absence of light. Hence it can be concluded that light in the treatment of disease, is likely to act as a stimulant of body cells and accelerator of metabolism, as the oxidation of food material is accelerated by light.

Influence of Light on Plant Respiration.

Dhar and collaborators have shown that the food materials like starch, sugars, proteins and fats in aqueous solutions or suspensions are oxidised to carbon dioxide and water by simply passing air at the ordinary temperature in presence of sunlight. In absence of light, there is no oxidation. In presence of inductors like ferrous hydroxide, cerous hydroxide, glutathione, etc., the food materials are oxidised to carbon dioxide and water by air even in absence of light. In presence of sunlight these induced oxidations are greatly increased. It appears, therefore, that the sunlight absorbed by the plants will also accelerate the oxidation of glucose and other food materials present in the plant. Hence in presence of light the respiration in the plant is likely to be increased.

The experimental observations of Miss Matthaei (1905), Rose (1910) Shri Ranjan (1932), Parija and co-workers (1933) and others seem to indicate the accelerating influence of light on plant respiration.

The following observations can be explained from the view point that light accelerates respiration in plants :

The velocity of respiration of plants growing in shade is generally much less than in plants growing in light. Light retards growth and the higher the intensity of light, the greater the retardation. The retarding effect of light, on the aerial organs of plants is well observed on mountain tops, where the solar radiations are richer in ultraviolet radiations than in plains.

It is well known that not only higher temperature but also long exposure to strong light adversely affects photosynthetic activity. It appears that plants growing on mountain tops receive more ultraviolet radiations, which are less favourable for carbon assimilation than red light but ultraviolet light accelerates the oxidation processes markedly. Hence in presence of light rich in ultraviolet radiations, the accumulation of carbonaceous matter in plants due to photosynthesis and hence growth are likely to be less because of the intensification of the opposing process *i.e.*, respiration, by the absorption of light energy. Because of the enhanced respiration in presence of light, the growth of the plant is likely to be retarded. This effect seems to be allied to the phenomenon of "solarisation."

It is well known that when plants are cultivated under conditions of high light intensity, they utilise only a small amount of the absorbed energy for photosynthesis. Plants growing in presence of feeble light can convert a relatively larger proportion of the absorbed energy into carbonaceous compounds. This behavior appears to be due to the intensification of respiration partly by absorption of light and partly by increase of temperature caused by the absorption of the incident radiations when the light is strong. This enhancement of respiration will minimise the photosynthetic effect.

Moreover with increasing temperature, the "compensation point" should rise more rapidly than the velocity of respiration because of its additional enhancement by light absorption and this is clearly borne out from the experiments on *cladophora*, in which an increase of temperature from 5° to 25° causes the respiration to become 4.8 times greater when determined in the dark, whilst the light intensity increases 6.69 times for the compensation point.

It has been assumed by most of the plant physiologists that the process of respiration is not accelerated by light absorption but the foregoing considerations seem to prove that light also accelerates respiration in both plants and animals. Several other aspects of the

influence of light on plant respiration were discussed in my last address (cf. *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 145.)

Influence of Light on Ammonification and Nitrification.

In recent publications it has been shown that light plays an important rôle in the phenomena of nitrification and ammonification. Gopala Rao and Dhar (1931) have observed that ammonia is slowly oxidised in aqueous solution to nitrite, when exposed to the light from a quartz mercury vapour lamp and copper arc and more slowly in sunlight. The oxidation of ammonia solutions takes place even in light filtered through a 5% quinine sulphate solution of 4 cm. thickness, which cuts off radiations shorter than $4200 \text{ \AA}$. Ammonium salts are also oxidised to nitrites, the reaction being slower in the case of the sulphate and chloride than with phosphate and carbonate.

The velocity of the photo-oxidation of aqueous solutions of ammonia and its salts is considerably increased by the presence of photosensitisers like titania, zinc, and cadmium oxides, alumina, silica, magnesia, etc. Titania is the most and silica is the least active in this photo-oxidation. The p_H of the solution has a profound influence on the reaction velocity; alkalinity increases the velocity of oxidation of ammonium salts and acidity decreases the oxidation. The velocity of the oxidation is greater in quartz vessels than in glass ones. The accumulation of nitrite appears to have no influence on the velocity of the oxidation of ammonia and its salts photochemically.

Recently Dhar, Bhattacharya and Biswas (1932-33) have shown that large amounts of ammonium salts are converted into nitrite and nitrate in presence of light and air but very little oxidation takes place in the dark when ammonium salts and sterilised or unsterilised soil are allowed to oxidise in air. It has been shown that the oxidation of ammonium salts mixed with sterilised or unsterilised soil in covered vessels coated with Japan black enamel (*i.e.* receiving no light) when kept in the sun along with the vessels receiving light is much smaller than in those exposed to light. If nitrification were mainly a bacterial process the amount of nitrification in the vessels in the dark with the unsterilised soil should not have been materially different from those exposed to light. We have made numerous comparative experiments like those on the oxidation of ammonium salts to nitrite and of nitrite to nitrate with both sterilised and unsterilised soil kept in light and in dark and we find that the formation of nitrite and nitrate is

always much greater in the vessels exposed to light than in those kept in the dark.

The photolysis of various amino acids in sunlight has been studied by Gopala Rao and Dhar (1934) and Dhar and Mukherji (1934). These amino acids decompose with the liberation of ammonia. The decomposition appears to be one of oxidative de-amination, because by passing oxygen or air through the solution of the amino acids the amount of ammonia liberated is increased. The aliphatic amino acids, *e.g.*, glycine are oxidised in the presence of air and sunlight with the formation of the corresponding aldehyde, ammonia and carbon dioxide. This is represented by the general equation,

In most of the cases, the amount of ammoniacal nitrogen formed by photolysis was found to correspond quantitatively to the decrease in amino-nitrogen.

In the light of the above experimental evidence, the author believes that the formation of ammonia in the soil from amino acids obtained from protein decomposition is mainly an oxidative de-amination, accelerated by sunlight. We have shown that aqueous solutions of amino acids photolyse in the presence of photo-sensitisers like titanium dioxide, aluminium oxide, humic acid, zinc oxide, etc. When we keep in mind that the first three substances normally occur in all soils, it will be clear that ammonification in soils can take place without the presence of bacteria or fungi, if only sunlight be present.

Recently it has been observed by us that dilute solutions of sodium or potassium nitrite are almost completely oxidised to nitrate when exposed to light along with solid substances like TiO_2 , ZnO , Fe_2O_3 , and sterilised soil in the absence of bacteria. In other words, from the experimental work carried on in these laboratories, we find that not only are ammonium salts oxidised to nitrite by air in the presence of light but the nitrites are also in their turn, readily converted into nitrate when exposed to light and air along with sterilised soil or photocatalysts. It seems, therefore, that the whole process of nitrification can be photochemical. Moreover, it has been found by us that solutions of amino acids are readily oxidised to ammonia in the presence of air and light. Thus one of the important stages in the process of ammonification is also markedly accelerated by light.

Leather working at Pusa (India) stated that the maximum temperature at Pusa may rise to 70° at the soil surface and 60° at a depth of 1 or 2 inches. In Egypt the recorded temperature is 65° at the surface and 56° at a depth of 2 inches. Similar high temperatures have been recorded in the summer months at Allahabad. The measurements of S. P. Tandon and N. R. Dhar (1934) show that 35° is the optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification, which becomes practically negligible at 50°. Hence in tropics, nitrification in soil cannot be to any marked extent, of bacterial origin in the months of April, May, June, and July, when the soil temperature is much greater than the optimum for nitrification by bacteria. In these very months the amount of nitrate in soil is, however, the greatest. Even in colder countries, like England and Germany, the soil temperature may rise to 35° or more in summer, although the optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification is stated to be 25° in the cold countries. In these countries bacterial nitrification must be greatly reduced in the summer months as a result of the soil temperature becoming much greater than the optimum temperature for bacterial nitrification, though the nitrate content of the soil in these countries is also largest in the summer time.

It is believed that in moist soils, most of the bacteria are concentrated in the first 2 feet of the soil. The largest numbers are observed 1 to 3 inches below the surface. Because of the antiseptic properties of the solar radiations and the rapid evaporation of moisture from the soil surface, the number of bacteria is less on the surface. According to Waksman, (1916) soils under shade have the highest number of bacteria at a depth of 1 inch, and the number decreases with depth, whereas soils receiving sunlight contain the largest numbers of bacteria at a depth of 4 inches.

It is generally agreed that nitrification is most active at the surface of the soil. According to Prescott and Piper (1930) nearly 80% of the nitrate accumulation takes place in the first 3½ inches of the soil from the surface. From the observations recorded above it seems to us that the soil temperature in the summer months in tropical countries must not be much below 50° even at the depth of 3½ inches from the surface, although the bacterial nitrification has the optimum temperature of 35°. In Lyallpur, Punjab, in summer months, the soil temperature at 5 cm. depth is as high as 50° and at 30 cm. depth 37°. It appears, therefore, that in the first 3½ inches of the soil, where there is maximum nitrification as observed by

different investigators, very few bacteria can exist in tropical countries in summer months, although the amount of nitrate in soil is maximum in summer. We are led to conclude, therefore, that agencies other than bacterial must be active in causing nitrification, which is going on at a maximum speed in the soil in summer months within $3\frac{1}{2}$ inches of the soil. As we have observed that light markedly accelerates the oxidation of amino acids to NH_3 , of ammonium salts to nitrites, and of nitrites to nitrates, and that all these oxidations are accelerated by increase of temperature, we are led to believe that light absorption and increase of temperature play a more important rôle than bacteria in nitrification in summer months, when the nitrate content of the soil is known to be maximum in almost all countries.

The increase in fertility of soil as a result of exposure to sunlight as practised in India, Egypt, and other countries from time immemorial can be easily explained from our observations. The increased production of ammonia and nitrate by partial sterilisation of soil has been stated by authorities on agriculture to be not a necessary consequence of the higher number of the organisms present on the soil. As nitrification is essentially an oxidation reaction taking place on the soil surface, the various agencies, *e.g.*, increase in the aeration, soil surface, the temperature upto a limiting value, will increase nitrification. Moreover, sunlight or diffused light is always available and accelerates the formation of NH_3 from amino acids, and the oxidation of NH_3 to nitrite and of nitrite to nitrate. It appears, that the increase in fertility of soil on heating or exposure to sunlight, as is done by cultivators in many countries, is mainly due to increased oxidation of nitrogenous compounds, especially of the amino acids, causing the formation of NH_3 and to increased nitrification brought about by the soil becoming more porous and by the accentuation of the air supply and above all by the increased light absorption. When a soil is ploughed, fresh surfaces are exposed to sunlight and air and ammonification and nitrification are facilitated. In this connection, the following statement of Russell (1932) is of interest:—"Ammonia production in soil, however, is not entirely the result of direct action of micro-organisms. It goes on even in presence of antiseptics."

It is gratifying to find that our observations on the influence of light on soil processes are being corroborated by workers in different tropical stations. Thus Sarkaria and Fazal Uddin (Lyallpur, 1933) have observed marked ammonification and nitrification of several nitrogenous

compounds and nitrification of ammonium salts and oxidation of sodium nitrite to nitrate in presence of sunlight aided by photocatalysts in the absence of bacteria. It is of interest to record here the following observations of two bacteriologists regarding the influence of light on these soil processes in the tropical climates:—"I have been particularly interested in your very informative papers on the subject on photochemical nitrification which have come to my attention these recent years. The general underlying theory of your work is quite in harmony with some of the work I have been carrying on since my arrival in Hawaii. My early studies in nitrification of ammonium sulphate fertilisers in some of our Hawaiian soils were not explainable from a bacterial standpoint. The application of the photochemical idea is proving a very worthwhile venture" (Allen, University of Hawaii). "From my experience in Malaya, where I was particularly struck by the paucity of soil micro-organisms, I should think your results on photonitrication are of quite general application in tropical countries" (Corbet, Agricultural Researches Station Bracknell, Berkshire).

Denitrification in Sunlight and its Retardation.

The researches of different investigators show that nitrogen in the gaseous state is lost from soils when the conditions are favourable for oxidation. The loss of nitrogen in this process may be double the amount of nitrogen taken up by the plant grown on the soil.

A greater loss of nitrogen is observed when a manure is composted under aerobic than anaerobic conditions. There is more loss of nitrogen from stable manure in presence of nitrifying bacteria than in their absence. It has also been reported that in the nitrification of different oil-cakes, the loss of nitrogen is the greatest with the most easily and quickly nitrifiable cakes. Greater velocity of oxidation and greater nitrogen loss have been observed with ammonium salts than with farm-yard and green manures on nitrification. Moreover, when there is a large amount of carbonaceous matter present in the manures along with nitrogenous compounds, the velocity of the oxidation of nitrogenous compounds and the amount of nitrogen loss are also decreased.

Experiments carried on at different places show that the total amount of nitrate present in soils containing crops is less than that in neighbouring fallow soils even when a correction is applied

for the amount of nitrate taken up by the crop. The oxidation processes are more vigorous in soils with crops than in those without them.

Our experimental results show that the loss of nitrogen on exposing ammonium salt solutions to light and air is always greater in light than in the dark. The oxidation of ammonium salts by air is greater in light than in the dark and hence the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite is greater in light than in the dark. Moreover, solutions of ammonium chloride and sodium nitrite decompose readily with evolution of nitrogen when exposed to sunlight in open beakers mixed with sterilised and unsterilised soils. This decomposition is considerably less in dilute solutions of ammonium nitrite and also when cane sugar is added to the solution containing ammonium and nitrite ions.

All these observations have been explained from the view point that in the processes of ammonification, and nitrification taking place in the soil or in solutions, ammonium nitrite is produced. Solutions of ammonium nitrite have been found to be decomposed into nitrogen and water readily by increase of temperature or exposing them to light. The formation of ammonium nitrite from ammonium salts or proteins requires oxygen and that is why, this type of dinitrification is facilitated by increased soil aeration and also soil acidity as nitrous acid also undergoes decomposition according to the equation,

Addition of carbonaceous substances like molasses tends to preserve the soil nitrogen by decreasing the velocity of the oxidation of the nitrogenous compounds present in the soil and thus decreasing the probability of the formation and decomposition of ammonium nitrite.

Of course, too little oxidation of the protein present in the soil by the addition of molasses will not make the soil suitable for the growth of crops. It seems necessary that an equilibrium should be established between the oxidised and the unoxidised proteins, ammonium salts and other nitrogenous substances, which are present in the soil for maintaining its fertility at a proper level. Too much oxidation of the nitrogenous substances, and ammonium salts may entail marked nitrogen loss by this type of dinitrification, and too little oxidation will not make the soil fertile enough for a good

yield of crop. Hence the molasses should not be added in very large amounts and after the addition of molasses, the soil should be ploughed several times to help oxidation. Moreover, molasses when added to soil in moderate amounts and the soil is properly aerated for helping the oxidation reactions, cause nitrogen fixation as evidenced by the increase of ammoniacal nitrogen content of soil.

Nitrogen Fixation in Soils by the Application of Molasses.

Our results obtained with soil and cane sugar on exposure to sunlight and air show that both with sterilised and unsterilised soils, the ammoniacal nitrogen goes on increasing upto a limiting value with time, although the nitric nitrogen remains constant during this time. After this period further exposure to light leads to a decrease in ammoniacal nitrogen and an increase of nitric nitrogen but the sum of the ammoniacal and nitric nitrogen is less than that obtained before. This behaviour is due to a loss of nitrogen caused by the photochemical and catalytic decomposition of ammonium nitrite formed on the soil surface. It is well known that 90% of the nitrogen fixed by *Azotobacter* exists as ammonia, and that is why the ammonia increases when the unsterilised soil is exposed to light mixed with sugar. It is surprising that even in the sterilised soil ammonia goes on increasing. Both the soils were tested bacteriologically after exposure for *Azotobacter*, which was readily obtained in the unsterilised soil. After culture only a few could be detected in the sterilised ones. It seems that the combination of nitrogen and oxygen is induced by the oxidation of sugars present in the soil. The nitrite and nitrate formed are readily reduced to ammonia by the reducing action of the sugars, and that is why only ammonia is increased and not nitrate. In a recent communication from this laboratory it has been shown that the optimum temperature for nitrogen fixation by *Azotobacter* is 35°, whilst at 45° practically no nitrogen fixation by *Azotobacter* takes place. It seems, therefore, that the nitrogen fixation during summer days by bacteria will be exceedingly small because they will be mostly killed by the intense heat and light which the soil receives. Our results show that the fixation of nitrogen in the soil by the addition of sugar is helped by light and may take place even in the absence of *Azotobacter*. In the absence of bacteria, hardly any fixation of nitrogen in the soil takes place in the dark.

After obtaining definite evidence regarding the fixation of nitrogen by the addition of sugar both in the sterilised and unsterilised soils, we extended our experiments on the fixation of nitrogen under ordinary field conditions by the addition of molasses. 35 Kilos of molasses were added to an area of 500 sq. ft. and the area was divided into two parts, one part was dug several times after the addition of molasses and the other part was not ploughed.

Our observations show that the ammoniacal nitrogen is about 10 times greater in soil after the addition of molasses and aeration even when correction is applied for the addition of ammonia added with molasses. The nitrogen fixed in the soil on the addition of carbohydrates, exists chiefly as ammonia and hence the ammoniacal nitrogen content of a soil is higher on the addition of molasses. From these experiments it can be concluded that considerable fixation of nitrogen takes place in tropical soils on the addition of molasses provided the aeration of the soil is sufficient. When the aeration is incomplete nitrogen fixation becomes defective because energy is necessary for nitrogen fixation and this energy comes from the oxidation of sugars and that is why a large supply of air is necessary. In the absence of air, anaerobic bacteria and fungi flourish and utilise the carbohydrates and nitrate for their growth and hence in the presence of bacteria, instead of addition of nitrogen to soil, nitrate is lost, as has been observed by different people. Moreover, this oxidation is facilitated by increase of temperature and sunlight and hence there is a great possibility for the utilisation of molasses in India as a manure in increasing the soil nitrogen, which is the crying need of tropical soils, provided there is sufficient aeration and the soil is exposed to sunlight. The carbohydrates present in molasses will undergo oxidation in the soil liberating energy necessary for the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen. Thus by the addition of carbohydrates the soil fertility with regard to combined nitrogen can be easily increased. If the acidity of the soil is increased on the addition of molasses, some calcium carbonate has to be added to the soil for the neutralisation of the acid. It is found that the growth of wheat is the best on the portion of the soil containing molasses and well turned over and on the portion containing molasses but not aerated, the growth seems slightly inferior to that on the portion containing no molasses but well aerated by digging.

Many workers have failed to obtain nitrogen fixation in soils on the addition of carbohydrates. It seems that the failure is mainly due to

the insufficiency of aeration in the soil. In cold countries, the velocity of the oxidation of the energy rich substances present in the soil may be very small and thus the energy available from the oxidation of sugar may be too small for marked nitrogen fixation. In tropical countries, however, if the soil is well ploughed after the addition of carbohydrates, there is no reason, why the soil fertility regarding combined nitrogen should not be increased.

I have begun my address with a dictum of Lavoisier and it is fitting that I should end it with the following lines written by the great French Chemist not long before his tragic end by the guillotine :—

“To merit well of humanity and to pay tribute to one’s country it is not necessary to take part in brilliant public functions that have to do with the organisation and regeneration of empires. The naturalist may also perform patriotic functions in the silence of his laboratory and at his desk ; he can hope through his labours to diminish the mass of ills which afflict the human race or to increase its happiness and pleasure ; and should he by some new methods which he has opened up prolong the average life of men by years or even by days he can also aspire to the glorious title of benefactor of humanity.”
